

Influence Of Jahn–Teller (Cu²⁺) Ions Substitution On Charge Carrier Mobility And Seebeck Coefficient Of Nickel Ferrites

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Abstract:

Polycrystalline ferrite samples of $Ni_{1-x}Cu_xFe_2O_4$ ($x = 0.0, 0.2, \text{ and } 0.6$) were synthesized using the standard double-sintering ceramic technique to investigate the effect of Cu^{2+} ion substitution on the charge carrier mobility and Seebeck coefficient. X-ray diffraction confirmed mono-phase cubic spinel structures for all compositions. The electrical conductivity and thermoelectric power were measured in the temperature range 300–950 K. The results reveal that conductivity increases with Cu content due to enhanced Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} hopping and reduced activation energy. The Seebeck coefficient is negative, indicating n-type semiconducting behavior dominated by electron conduction. Its value decrease up to certain temperature and then start increasing, consistent with small-polaron hopping conduction. The enhanced carrier mobility and tunable thermoelectric properties make Cu-doped nickel ferrites potential candidates for spintronic and thermoelectric applications.

Keywords: Ni–Cu ferrite; n-type semiconductor; Seebeck coefficient; charge carrier mobility; small-polaron hopping.

Introduction:

Nickel ferrite ($NiFe_2O_4$) is an inverse spinel ferrite that exhibits semiconducting behavior and high chemical stability, making it suitable for electronic, magnetic, and thermoelectric applications [1–3]. Its electrical and thermoelectric properties arise mainly from electron hopping between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions occupying octahedral [B] sites [4]. The cation distribution between tetrahedral (A) and octahedral [B] sites strongly influences carrier mobility and conduction type [5]. Substitution of Cu^{2+} ions for Ni^{2+} in $NiFe_2O_4$ modifies the lattice parameters and the Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} ratio, leading to changes in electronic transport and thermoelectric behavior [6,7]. Cu^{2+} is a Jahn–Teller active ion, which introduces local distortions in the

octahedral sites, thereby affecting hopping probability and charge mobility [8]. In ferrites, the Seebeck coefficient (S) provides key information about the dominant carrier type — positive for holes (p-type) and negative for electrons (n-type) [9]. The charge carrier mobility (μ) and electrical conductivity (σ) together determine the efficiency of thermoelectric conversion. This study aims to investigate the influence of Cu substitution on the charge carrier mobility and Seebeck coefficient of $Ni_{1-x}Cu_xFe_2O_4$ ($x = 0.0, 0.2, 0.6$) synthesized by the double-sintering method. Emphasis is given to understanding the transition in conduction behavior and its correlation with structural and electronic modifications.

Experimental Details:

1. Synthesis: Analytical-grade NiO, CuO, and Fe₂O₃ powders were used to prepare samples with nominal compositions Ni_{1-x}Cu_xFe₂O₄ (x = 0.0, 0.2, 0.6). The powders were weighed stoichiometrically, mixed thoroughly in an agate mortar with ethanol for 6 hr, and pre-sintered at 1293 °K for 12 hr. The powders were then re-ground, pressed into pellets (10 mm diameter, 2 mm thickness) under 6-ton/inch² pressure, and sintered at 1353 °K for 13 hr. in air. The sintered samples were cooled slowly to room temperature.

2. Structural Characterization: X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was carried out at room temperature using a Cu-K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2θ range of 20°–80°. Lattice parameters were determined using least-squares fitting of the major diffraction peaks, confirming a cubic spinel structure. Crystallite sizes were determined using the Scherrer formula.

$$D = 0.9\lambda / \beta \cos\theta$$

3. Electrical and Thermoelectric Measurements: DC electrical conductivity (σ) and Seebeck coefficient (S) were measured simultaneously in the temperature range 300–950 K using a custom-built setup. The charge carrier mobility (μ) was estimated from:

$$\mu = \sigma / ne$$

where n is the carrier concentration derived from the small-polaron hopping model. Activation energy (E_a) was obtained from the slope of $\ln(\sigma T)$ vs. $1/T$ plots using the relation:

$$\sigma T = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$$

Results And Discussion:

1. Structural Analysis: The XRD patterns of all compositions (Fig. 1) confirm the formation of a mono-phase cubic spinel structure without impurity peaks. The major reflections (220), (311), (400), (511), and (440) match well with the JCPDS card no. 74–2081 for NiFe₂O₄ [10].

Fig. 1: Typical XRD Pattern of Ni_{1-x}Cu_xFe₂O₄ (x=0.2)

The lattice constant increases gradually with Cu substitution (Table 1), consistent with the larger ionic radius of Cu²⁺ (0.72 Å) compared to Ni²⁺ (0.69 Å) [11]. The crystallite size decreases slightly with increasing Cu content due to enhanced lattice strain and grain boundary distortion.

Table 1. Structural parameters of Ni_{1-x}Cu_xFe₂O₄ ferrites.

Sr. No.	Comp.(x)	Lattice constant (Å)	Crystallite size (μm)
1	0.0	8.3250	36.380
2	0.2	8.3285	35.26
3	0.6	8.3748	36.61

2. Electrical Conductivity and Charge Carrier Mobility

Table 2. Charge Carrier Mobility (μ) and Temp. (K) of Ni_{1-x}Cu_xFe₂O₄.

Sr. No	Temp.(K)	μ (cm ² /Vs)		
		x = 0.0	x = 0.2	x = 0.6
1	650	3.30	3.9	5.61
2	700	4.44	16.0	12.75
3	750	5.61	19.9	46.0
4	780	12.8	29.0	62.0
5	810	18.5	35.0	96.0
6	830	24.8	60.0	126.0
7	890	60.0	127.0	220.0
8	925	100.0	175.0	263.0
9	975	153.0	250.0	367.0

Fig. 2: Charge Carrier Mobility (μ) with Temp.(T) of $Ni_{1-x}Cu_xFe_2O_4$.

Figure 2 shows the variation of charge carrier mobility with temperature. All samples exhibit semiconducting behavior, where charge carrier mobility increases exponentially with temperature due to thermally activated hopping of electrons between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions at octahedral sites [12]. Conductivity increases with Cu content, indicating enhanced electron hopping probability and improved carrier mobility. (Table 2). The enhancement in carrier mobility with Cu substitution arises from structural distortion and increased Fe^{2+} ion concentration, which promote $Fe^{2+}-O-Fe^{3+}$ electron hopping across octahedral sites [13].

3. Seebeck Coefficient and Thermoelectric Behavior: The Seebeck coefficient (S) for all samples is negative throughout the measured temperature range (Fig. 3), confirming n-type conduction, where electrons are the dominant charge carriers.

Fig. 3: Typical TEP Pattern of $Ni_{1-x}Cu_xFe_2O_4$ ($x=0.2$)

The magnitude of S decreases with temperature, indicating typical small-polaron hopping behavior in ferrites [14]. The absolute value of S decreases with increasing Cu content, which is consistent with the observed rise in conductivity and carrier concentration. The Seebeck coefficient in ferrites is inversely related to carrier concentration (n) according to

$$S = -\frac{k_B}{e} \ln \left(\frac{n_c}{n} \right)$$

where n_c is the effective density of states [15]. The negative sign indicates electron-dominated transport. The power factor ($S^2\sigma$) increases slightly for $x = 0.2$ due to a balance between moderate Seebeck coefficient and enhanced conductivity, implying potential for low-temperature thermoelectric applications [16].

4. Conduction Mechanism: Charge transport in Ni–Cu ferrites occurs via thermally activated small-polaron hopping between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions located at octahedral sites. The substitution of Cu^{2+} ions modifies cation distribution, reduces Fe–O–Fe bond length, and enhances orbital overlap, thereby improving electron mobility [17]. Furthermore, Cu^{2+} ($3d^9$) introduces local lattice distortions due to the Jahn–Teller effect, lowering the potential barrier for electron hopping. The observed correlation between decreased activation energy, increased mobility, and negative Seebeck coefficient confirms that Cu substitution enhances n-type conduction in $NiFe_2O_4$ [18,19].

Conclusion:

Polycrystalline $Ni_{1-x}Cu_xFe_2O_4$ ($x = 0.0, 0.2, 0.6$) ferrites were successfully synthesized using the ceramic route. All samples exhibit single-phase cubic spinel structures. Electrical conductivity and carrier mobility increase, while activation energy and the magnitude of the Seebeck coefficient decrease with Cu content. The negative Seebeck coefficient confirms n-type conduction, dominated by electron hopping

between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions. The optimized transport behavior at $x = 0.2$ suggests potential for applications in thermoelectric and spin-caloritronic devices.

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